

1 **Hnf1b functions in embryonic stem cell fate choice during endoderm lineage specification.**

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6 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
7 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
8 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
9 describe a requirement for Hnf1b in germ layer lineage choice from pluripotent stem cells in *Homo*
10 *sapiens*.

11 Citations

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